

STUDY OF POLYMER COATINGS IMPLANTED WITH HIGH-ENERGY ION BEAMS

¹B.D. Igamov, ²A.I. Kamardin, ³I.Yu.Kochemasov, ⁴I.R. Bekpulatov, ⁵A.M. Normamatov, ⁶F.B. Norboyeva

^{1,2,3}Scientific and Technical Center with a Design Bureau and Pilot Production, Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Uzbekistan

^{4,5,6}Karshi State University 180119, Karshi, Uzbekistan

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15436982>

The starting samples for the research were polished monocrystalline silicon plates KDB-10, glass plates (K-8), and polished steel samples. Preliminarily, the silicon and glass plates were cleaned by boiling in a peroxide-ammonia solution ($\text{H}_2\text{O}_2:\text{NH}_4\text{OH}:\text{H}_2\text{O}=8:1:1$), concentrated sulfuric acid (H_2SO_4), rinsed in deionized water, and dried in a centrifuge at a rotor speed of up to 3500 rpm.

As studies have shown, all polymer coatings behave similarly when irradiated with ion beams. For ion doses exceeding 10^{14} - 10^{15} cm^{-2} , a noticeable color change occurs in the coatings, from light or light yellow to brown and gray-black. At doses higher than 10^{16} cm^{-2} , polymer coatings typically undergo destruction, forming cracks and blisters. The most significant destruction is observed in coatings with a thickness greater than 1.0-1.5 μm when treated with ions of mass greater than 30 a.m.u.

Studies of the physicochemical properties of polymer coatings, particularly positive photoresists, irradiated by various ions with energies up to 150 keV and doses up to 10^{17} cm^{-2} , show that implantation induces polymer degradation and their transformation into a carbon-like diamond state. The final properties of the polymer coatings are influenced by the relationship between the average ion penetration depths and the thickness of the coatings, as well as the ion mass and irradiation dose. The most effective modification of polymers and their transition into a diamond-like carbon state occurs when irradiating coatings with thicknesses less than 300 nm using relatively heavy ions with energies greater than 120 keV and doses around 10^{16} cm^{-2} or gas mixtures.